

DEVELOPMENT OF CARBON FIBRE REINFORCED EPOXY COMPOSITES WITH CONTROLLABLE STIFFNESS

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Abstract

High performance carbon fibre reinforced composites with controllable stiffness could be used in applications such as morphing wings. These morphing aerostructures could improve the efficiency of aircraft by lowering drag and reducing weight. A significant challenge in the field of morphing aerostructures is the development of a stiff skin material that can transfer aerodynamic loads but that can be easily deformed when a shape change is required. Here we describe two designs of carbon fibre reinforced epoxy composite with controllable stiffness that could be used as skin materials in morphing wings. When the composites are heated to elevated temperatures they can undergo reductions in flexural stiffness of up to 98 % and fully recover when cooled to room temperature. Controllable stiffness materials may also find applications in deployable and collapsible structures.

1. Introduction

A morphing wing can be described as a seamless structure that can undergo a continuous change of shape [1]. If a shape change is required in a morphing wing then the whole structure can be deformed upon actuation. This differs from conventional wings that consist of a large number of traditional components such as flaps and ailerons, hydraulically independent of one another. When compared with conventional wing designs there are a number of benefits associated with the use of morphing wings, including reduced weight and drag [2, 3]. In order to develop an effective morphing wing, a skin material is required that can withstand aerodynamic loads but that can be deformed on demand at relatively low actuation forces [4]. A composite with controllable stiffness could be a

suitable skin material as it offers high stiffness prior to actuation and low stiffness and high strain to failure at elevated temperatures.

Controllable stiffness materials have been developed previously for use in morphing applications. Henry and McKnight developed a composite consisting of a Shape Memory Polymer (SMP) reinforced with discontinuous steel [5]. When the composite was heated above the T_g of the SMP, the storage modulus was reduced by up to 99 %, measured using Dynamic Mechanical Thermal Analysis (DMTA). A problem with designs such as these is that structural deformations can only occur when the matrix has softened. Therefore, when these composites are deformed at elevated temperature there is a possibility the reinforcement could misalign, resulting in permanent damage.

Multi-layered beams with variable stiffness were developed by Gandhi et al [6-8]. The beams consisted of aluminium layers separated by cast acrylic and polyvinyl chloride (PVC) type material. The polymer layers were heated through their glass transition temperatures using embedded electric heating blankets. The flexural stiffness of the beams at room temperature was up to four times greater than at elevated temperature.

A glass fibre reinforced polymer (GFRP) - carbon fibre reinforced polymer (CFRP) composite beam with controllable stiffness was designed for vibration damping applications [9]. The bending stiffness of the beam was controlled by applying an electric field between the GFRP and CFRP elements, hence using electrostatic coupling of the layers to control the stiffness. These beams were not designed to undergo large deflections and are therefore unsuitable for morphing applications.

Raither and colleagues [10] developed a variable stiffness CFRP laminate containing alternating layers of elastomer. The CFRP layers had different fibre orientations and this permitted adaptive bend-twist coupling of the composite when the elastomer was heated above its T_g (44 °C). The low T_g of the elastomer would limit the use of this composite in aerostructures where high operating temperature are required. For the concepts described in this paper, polystyrene was chosen as the thermo-responsive material as its T_g is approximately 100 °C.

2. The Concept

In this paper we describe two designs of carbon fibre reinforced epoxy composite with controllable stiffness. In the first design, each fibre within a polymer matrix composite is coated with a thin thermoplastic layer. Heating the thermoplastic coating until it softens allows the fibres to slide within the matrix (this heating can be achieved by passing a current through the carbon fibre reinforcement). This greatly reduces the flexural stiffness of the composite. The matrix can be either a thermoset or a thermoplastic provided that its glass transition temperature (T_g) is above the softening temperature or T_g of the thermoplastic coating. Polystyrene was selected as the thermoplastic coating as its softening temperature is above room temperature and yet below the T_g of the epoxy matrix at 175 °C.

The second design is a polystyrene interleaved carbon fibre reinforced epoxy composite. Heating the composite to 120 °C, above the T_g of the polystyrene, softens the interleaf layers and allows the reinforced plies to slide relative to each other. This dramatically reduces the flexural stiffness of the composite and permits large deflections at low actuation forces.

3. Experimental

3.1 Coating polystyrene continuously onto carbon fibres

Polystyrene was coated continuously onto carbon fibres via an in situ polymerisation process conducted inside a fume hood (see Fig. 1). 30 m AS4 unsized carbon fibres were wound onto a custom made PTFE roller and a 580 g pretension applied. The fibres were passed over a stainless steel pin (6 mm diameter, 1 mm wall thickness, 316L, FTI Ltd., East Sussex, UK) and into a glass bath (92

mm width, 370 mm and 88 mm height, IKEA, UK) containing two custom made PTFE rollers. A 1.76 mol/dm³ styrene ($\geq 99\%$, Sigma Aldrich) in water mixture was added to the bath and heated to 50 °C whilst being stirred using a hotplate with a magnetic stirrer. 3.18 g/dm³ of water soluble azo initiator (VA-057, Wako Chemicals, Germany) was added. A second stainless steel pin was placed after the bath over which the fibres were placed. 1.4 A were applied to the stainless steel pins using a power supply (Statron, TYP 3218, GDR, Germany) to heat the carbon fibres to 85 °C. The carbon fibres were collected onto a cardboard drum (83 mm diameter, 3 mm wall thickness) using a custom built fibre winding unit with a brushless DC Motor (FBLM5120W-GFB/ GFB5G200, VEXTA, Oriental Motor Co., Ltd., Japan) at a speed of 0.14 m/min.

3.2 Filament winding carbon fibres

The cardboard tube onto which the fibres were wound was placed onto a tension control machine (CTS setting panel, Izumi international, Japan). The fibres were then placed over a force detector (DTH 6120, Izumi international, Japan) and 120 g tension applied. The fibres were wound onto a release fabric (FF03PM, Aerovac, West Yorkshire, UK) covered aluminium plate (75 mm width, 200 mm length and 3 mm thickness) at 10 rpm using a filament winding machine (Kolelectric, Middlesex, UK). The fibres were guided onto the plate using a single, custom made, PTFE roller. Two layers of carbon fibres were wound. Epoxy resin (Araldite LY 556/ Hardener XB 3473, Huntsman, UK) was brushed onto the release fabric covered plate prior to winding and then between the first and second layers of carbon fibres to ensure complete infusion of the epoxy. The epoxy was prepared using a resin to hardener mixing ratio of 100:23 by mass. The release fabric and the ends of the fibre tows were taped to the metal plate using Hi-Bond Polystyrene Adhesive Tape (25 mm \times 33 mm, RS, Korea).

3.3 Fabrication of polystyrene coated carbon fibre reinforced epoxy composite

Resin Infusion under Flexible Tooling (RIFT) was used to infuse, consolidate and cure the specimens. To prepare the bagging setup for the resin infusion process, a polyester film (450 \times 800 mm, Melinex, PW 122-10 50-RL, PSG group, UK) was taped onto a heating plate (460 mm \times 920 mm, Wenesco, Inc.,

USA) using high temperature resistant tape (Flashtape 1, Aerovac, West Yorkshire, UK). A release fabric (360 × 700 mm, FF03PM, Aerovac, West Yorkshire, UK) was placed onto the Melinex film, followed by a layer of polyester flow media (360 × 500 mm, Resin Diffuse Membrane, 1507B, Newbury Engineer Textile, Berkshire, UK). The fibre preforms were then placed between two layers of the release fabric. A layer of resin diffusion membrane was placed on top of that. Two Legris fluoropolymer tubes (6 mm internal diameter, RS Components, UK) were positioned either end of the set-up. The inlet was bent several times in order to prevent air getting into the system when the vacuum was pulled. The outlet was connected to a vacuum pump (Island Scientific, Isle of Wight, UK). The system was sealed using vacuum bagging film (600 mm × 1000 mm, Capran 518 heat stabilised Nylon 6 blown tubular film, Aerovac, West Yorkshire, UK) and sealant tape (SM5127, Aerovac, West Yorkshire, UK). A vacuum (10⁵ Pa) was then applied to remove air from the vacuum bag. The inlet tube was placed into the resin container once the required pressure had been reached. The epoxy resin (LY 556/ XB 3473) was allowed to flow over the sample at 40 °C and stopped once it had completely passed through the fibre preforms. The curing cycle (2 h at 120 °C and 4 h at 180 °C) was programmed using a temperature controller (Wenescio, Inc., USA). The cured composites were cut into 40 mm × 10 mm coupons for flexural testing and 40 mm × 5 mm test specimens for DMTA using a diamond bladed cutter (Diadisc 4200, Mutronic, Germany). The thicknesses of the uncoated and polystyrene coated fibre reinforced epoxy composite specimens were 0.96 ± 0.14 mm and 0.90 ± 0.09 mm, respectively.

3.4 Differential Scanning Calorimetry analysis of (coated) fibres

The thermal behaviour of the unsized and polystyrene coated carbon fibres was analysed using Differential Scanning Calorimetry (DSC Q2000 V24.4 Build 116, TA Instruments). The samples were heated from – 25 °C to 225 °C, cooled to – 25 °C and then reheated to 225 °C in a nitrogen atmosphere and at a heating and cooling rate of 10 °C/ min.

3.5 Diameter of (coated) fibres

The diameters of the carbon fibres were determined using the modified Wilhelmy-technique and calculated using equation 1.

$$d_f = \frac{m.g}{n.\pi.\cos \theta.\gamma_{lv}} \quad (1)$$

Where d_f = fibre diameter, n = number of fibres (5), m = mass difference after emersion and immersion of carbon fibres in dodecane (recorded using a 4504 MP8 Sartorius ultramicrobalance), θ = contact angle and γ_{lv} = surface tension of dodecane (25.4 mN/m, 99 %, Fisher Scientific). All measurements were taken at room temperature.

3.6 Interfacial shear strength of (coated) fibres to an epoxy matrix

Single fibre pull out tests were used to measure the interfacial shear strength (τ_{IFSS}), a measure of practical adhesion, between the carbon fibres (unmodified and coated) and the epoxy resin (LY 556/ XB 3473). The carbon fibres were embedded approximately 30-60 µm into the resin using a custom made embedding apparatus. The epoxy was then cured at 160 °C for 12 hours. A piezo-motor was used to pull the fibres out of the matrix at a speed of 0.2 µm/ s. The force was recorded by a load cell and logged using a computer. The interfacial shear strength was calculated from equation 2.

$$\tau_{IFSS} = \frac{F_{max}}{\pi.d_f.L} \quad (2)$$

Where d_f is the fibre diameter, F_{max} is the force maximum and L is the embedded length. The average interfacial shear strength was calculated from 8 measurements.

3.7 Fabrication of polystyrene films for interleaved flexural and compression tests specimens

5 g polystyrene pellets (ST316310, Goodfellow, UK) were arranged in a circular pattern (75 mm diameter) in the centre of a layer of polyimide release film (250 × 250 mm × 0.025 mm, UBE polyimide film, Upilex). Two additional release film layers of the same size were placed on top. A 190 mm diameter circle had been removed from the

centre of these films to restrict the flow of polystyrene during pressing. A complete layer of release film was used to enclose the polystyrene pellets. The films were placed between two stainless steel plates (250 mm × 240 mm × 3 mm) and put into a hot press (Model 4126 Manual, Hydraulic Press, Carver, USA) for 10 mins at 250 °C without pressure then at 3 ton for 40 minutes. The resulting polystyrene films were 126 ± 9 µm thick.

3.8 Fabrication of polystyrene films for interleaved tensile test specimens

10 g polystyrene pellets were distributed evenly in a circular pattern (75 mm diameter) between four layers of polyimide release film (250 × 250 mm × 0.025 mm). A 220 mm diameter circle had been removed from the centre of the two inner films. The release films were then placed between two stainless steel plates (250 mm × 240 mm × 3 mm) and put into a hot press for 10 minutes at 250 °C without pressure then at 3 ton for 40 minutes. The polystyrene films were 113 ± 25 µm thick.

3.9 Lay-up and production of interleaved composite

The interleaved composite consisted of 8 layers of polystyrene (126 ± 6 µm thick) and 9 plies of unidirectional carbon fibre reinforced epoxy (HexPly, 914C-TS-5-34%, Hexcel, 1 ply thickness = 0.126 µm) arranged in an alternating sequence. A 0° control sample consisting of 17 unidirectional reinforced plies was also manufactured (see Figure 2 for details of the interleaved and pure carbon fibre reinforced epoxy composites that have been manufactured and tested). All composite plates were 100 mm long in the 0° fibre direction by 150 mm wide, except the composite plates for tensile testing that were 210 mm long (0° direction) by 110 mm wide. The laminates were cured in a hot press (G969, George E Moore and Sons, UK) at 175 °C and 100 Psi for 1 h. The thickness of the interleaved composite was 2 ± 0.04 mm. The thickness of the 0° control sample was 2.14 ± 0.06 mm.

3.10 Preparation of flexure and DMTA specimens

The composites were cut into 80 mm × 10 mm coupons for flexural testing and 40 mm × 5 mm test specimens for DMTA using a diamond bladed cutter (Diadisc 4200, Mutronic, Germany). In both cases the 0° direction was parallel to the longer dimension of the specimen.

3.11 Preparation of tensile test specimens

The interleaved composite was cut into 200 mm × 100 mm specimens using a diamond blade cutter. The 0° direction was parallel to the longer dimension of the panel. Four glass fibre reinforced epoxy end tab plates (100 mm × 50 mm) with 45 ° chamfers were glued onto the grit blasted composite surface using epoxy glue (2014-1, Araldite, Huntsman). The epoxy was cured under vacuum for 24 h at room temperature. The resulting gauge length was 100 mm. The composites were then cut into 200 mm × 12 mm specimens using a diamond blade cutter and strain gauges (QFLA-2-11, Strain Gauges, Tokyo Sokki Kenkyujo Co., Ltd.) glued onto one side of the composite using adhesive (NP-50, TML Strain Gauge Adhesive, Tokyo Sokki Kenkyujo Co., Ltd.).

3.12 Preparation of compression test specimens

The interleaved composite was cut to the required dimensions (150 mm × 91 mm) using a diamond blade cutter. The 0° direction was parallel to the shorter dimension of the panel. Four glass fibre reinforced epoxy end tab plates (150 mm × 40 mm) with inverse chamfers were glued onto the grit blasted composite surface using epoxy glue (2014-1, Araldite, Huntsman). To ensure the gauge length remained at 10 mm during the epoxy curing; a silicon rubber shim was placed along the length of the gauge area. After curing under vacuum for 24 h at room temperature the shim was removed and the composite ground to a width of 90 mm using a grinder. The composites were then cut into 90 mm × 10 mm specimens using a diamond blade cutter and strain gauges (QFLA-2-11, Strain Gauges, Tokyo Sokki Kenkyujo Co., Ltd.) glued to both sides of the composite using adhesive (NP-50, TML Strain Gauge Adhesive, Tokyo Sokki Kenkyujo Co., Ltd.).

3.13 Evaluation of viscoelastic properties of composites

The viscoelastic behaviour of the composites was investigated using DMTA on a Tritec 2000 (Triton Technology Ltd., Keyworth, UK). Three point bending mode was performed at a gauge length of 15 mm and at a frequency of 1 Hz. A heating rate of 5 °C/ min from 30 °C to 230 °C was used.

3.14 Flexural tests

The flexural properties of the composites were determined using three point bending tests at both ambient and elevated temperatures according to ASTM D7264 [11]. The tests were carried out on an Instron 4505 (Bucks, UK) using a 1 kN load cell. A span-to-thickness ratio of 32:1 was used. The diameter of the loading nose and supports was 6 mm and a crosshead speed of 1 mm/ min was used. For one series of tests, specimens were loaded to a maximum deflection of 1 mm at room temperature (RT1) and then unloaded. The tests were then repeated at 120 °C in the environmental chamber (SFL, Eurotherm, West Sussex, UK) and then again at room temperature (RT2). The flexural strength was determined at room temperature by loading samples to failure that had not previously been tested. For some specimens a direct current was passed through the carbon fibres as an alternative method of heating. Both the upper and lower surfaces at each end of the samples were sanded down with sand paper and painted with silver conductive paint (186-3600, RS Components Ltd.). Copper tape was then wrapped around the silver paint and the loose ends of the tape connected to a power supply (HY3003-3, Digimess, UK). To heat a specimen to 120 °C, approximately 1.9 A and 2.8 V was needed for the unsized carbon fibre reinforced composites, 1.9 A and 2.5 V for the polystyrene coated carbon fibre reinforced composites, 1.8 A and 3 V for the interleaved composite and 1.3 A and 4 V for the non-interleaved composite (0° control sample).

The flexural modulus, E_f , of the specimens was calculated using equation 3, where L is support span, b is beam width, h is beam thickness and m is the gradient of the load - displacement curve. To calculate the average flexural modulus of the composites, five specimens of each sample were tested.

$$E_f = \frac{L^3 m}{4bh^3} \quad (3)$$

3.15 Tensile testing

Tensile tests were performed at room temperature on an Instron 4505 (Bucks, UK) with a 100 kN load cell. The tests were carried out in accordance with

ASTM D3039 [12]. The testing speed was 2 mm/ min.

3.16 Compression testing

Compression tests were performed at room temperature according to the Imperial College Compression Test method [13]. The tests were performed on an Instron 4505 (Bucks, UK) with a 100 kN load cell. The testing speed was 1 mm/ min.

4. Results and Discussion

4.1 Characterisation of polystyrene coated fibres

The fibre diameters of the carbon fibres, measured using the modified Wilhelmy-technique, can be seen in Table 1. The fibre diameter of the polystyrene coated fibres ($7.26 \pm 0.08 \mu\text{m}$) was larger than that of unmodified carbon fibres ($7.10 \pm 0.01 \mu\text{m}$) that suggests there is a thin layer of polystyrene on the fibre surface. The Interfacial Shear Strength (IFSS) of the unmodified and polystyrene coated fibres to an epoxy matrix was calculated using single fibre pull out tests. The IFSS for both fibres was approximately the same (Table 1). This shows that after modifying the fibre surface, the adhesion between the carbon fibres and the epoxy resin was unaffected. DSC was used to analyse the thermal properties of the coated fibres. The T_g of the polystyrene coating was recorded at 98 °C. No thermal transitions were seen for the unmodified carbon fibres.

4.2 Viscoelastic properties of polystyrene coated fibre reinforced composite

The DMTA curves for the unmodified carbon fibre reinforced composite showed a single transition at 174 °C, corresponding to the T_g of the epoxy. A 32 % decrease in the storage modulus, from 72 GPa to 49 GPa, was seen when the polystyrene coated carbon fibre composite when heated from room temperature to 120 °C. The T_g of the polystyrene coating was recorded at 110 °C from the first peak of the loss modulus. As the composite was heated from 120 °C to 230 °C the storage modulus dropped by 76 % to 12 GPa, associated with the T_g of the epoxy matrix.

4.3 Flexural properties of polystyrene coated fibre reinforced composite

At room temperature the flexural stiffness of the uncoated and polystyrene coated fibre reinforced

composites was 81 GPa (Table 2). When heated to 120 °C in an environmental chamber, the flexural modulus of the polystyrene coated fibre composite dropped by 30 % to 57 ± 5 GPa. The reduction in bending stiffness was higher when the composites were heated by passing a current through the carbon fibres. When the composite was heated from room temperature to 120 °C through an applied current, the flexural stiffness fell by 36 %. It is likely that the actual temperature around the carbon fibres was higher than the surface temperature of the composites (where the temperature was recorded) when using an applied current to heat the specimens. When the composite was cooled to room temperature the stiffness returned to its original value, showing the process is completely reversible. At 120 °C, the flexural modulus of the uncoated fibre reinforced composite was the same as its room temperature value.

4.4 Viscoelastic properties of interleaved composite

The storage modulus of the 0° control sample remained at approximately 123 GPa when heated from 30 °C to 140 °C, measured using DMTA. Above this temperature the storage modulus decreased due to the T_g of the epoxy resin at 175 °C. The interleaved composite was heated from 30 °C to 120 °C. The storage modulus at 30 °C was 58 GPa. The T_g of the polystyrene was calculated at 103 °C from the peak in the loss modulus. Above the glass transition, at 120 °C, the storage modulus dropped by 98 % to 1.2 GPa. The test was repeated three times on the same sample, from room temperature to 120 °C, to determine whether the process was reversible. The same stiffness loss and storage modulus at room temperature was observed in each case, showing that under these test conditions the process is completely reversible.

4.5 Flexural properties of interleaved composite

The flexural modulus of the interleaved composite at room temperature was 65 GPa. Above the T_g of polystyrene, at 120 °C, the modulus fell by 98 % to 1 GPa (Table 3). The composite was re-tested at room temperature and no loss in flexural modulus was observed. The specimens were heated to 120 °C using either an environmental chamber or an applied current. The flexural modulus values from both heating techniques were very similar. There was however extrusion of polystyrene near the electrical

contacts for the specimens heated using an applied current. It is likely that the temperature at the contacts exceeded the melting point of polystyrene and this caused the polymer to flow. When the composites were heating in an environmental chamber this problem did not occur. At 120 °C large deflections of the interleaved composite were achievable. The composites remained in the deformed state with very little spring-back when the temperature was lowered and the load was removed (Figure 3). The composites returned to their original configuration prior to bending when reheated without an applied load. This process could be repeated with no discernible damage or loss in properties (including variations in interleaf thickness).

4.6 Tensile and compressive properties of interleaved composite

The tensile and compressive properties of the interleaved composite were also measured at room temperature and 120 °C (Table 4). The tensile and compressive properties of the 0° control sample remained unchanged at elevated temperature. The tensile strength and modulus of the interleaved composite at room temperature was 867 ± 114 MPa and 88 ± 12 GPa, respectively. These values were approximately half those of the 0° control sample. This was expected as the interleaved composite contained around 50 % polystyrene. At 120 °C each ply within the interleaved composite was effectively disconnected and therefore for this layup the tensile strength dropped by 50 % to 395 ± 62 MPa. However, there was only a 32 % drop in stiffness, determined using data from a central strain gauge, at elevated temperature as some load was transferred to the inner CFRP plies. The compressive strength and modulus of the interleaved composite was 786 ± 64 MPa and 66 ± 1 GPa, respectively. These values were also half those of the 0° control sample at room temperature. At 120 °C the compressive properties of the interleaved composite were dramatically reduced and the specimen buckled within the gauge length. When the load was removed and the temperature was maintained at 120 °C the original shape of the composite was partly recovered.

5. Conclusion

A polystyrene coated carbon fibre reinforced epoxy composite with controllable stiffness was

manufactured. A 32 % reduction in storage modulus was recorded when the composite was heated from 30 °C to 120 °C using DMTA. No reduction in storage modulus occurred when the unmodified carbon fibre reinforced composite was heated to 120 °C. The flexural stiffness of the polystyrene coated fibre reinforced composite was also analysed using three point bending tests. The composite underwent a 30 % reduction in flexural stiffness when heated from room temperature to 120 °C and fully recovered when cooled.

A second design of controllable stiffness composite was also developed. An interleaved composite containing plies of polystyrene was manufactured. When analysed using DMTA, the composite underwent a 98 % loss in storage modulus from 30 °C to 120 °C. From three point bending tests the flexural modulus of the composite fell by 98 % when heated from room temperature to 120 °C. The composite could undergo large, reversible deflections at elevated temperature. After re-testing the composite at room temperature no loss in flexural stiffness was recorded.

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Fig. 1. Setup for the continuous grafting of polystyrene onto carbon fibres (where A are stainless steel pins and B are PTFE rollers).

Fig. 2. Layup sequence of the 0° control sample (left) and polystyrene interleaved composite (right).

Fig. 3. Straight and deformed polystyrene interleaved composites.

Carbon fibres	Fibre Diameter/ μm	Interfacial Shear Strength/ MPa
Unmodified AS4 fibres	7.10 ± 0.01	101.2 ± 2.6
Polystyrene coated fibres	7.26 ± 0.08	100.4 ± 7.0

Table 1. Fibre diameters and interfacial shear strengths of carbon fibres to an epoxy resin.

Reinforcement	Flexural Modulus/ GPa					
	Environmental chamber			Applied current		
	RT 1	120 °C	RT 2	RT 1	120 °C	RT 2
Uncoated carbon fibres	81 ± 8	81 ± 10	82 ± 6	85 ± 6	91 ± 7	87 ± 6
Polystyrene coated carbon fibres	81 ± 4	57 ± 5	85 ± 5	87 ± 3	56 ± 8	86 ± 9

Table 2. Flexural stiffness of uncoated and polystyrene coated carbon fibre reinforced epoxy composites at room temperature (RT) and 120 °C.

Composite	Flexural Modulus/ GPa					
	Environmental chamber			Applied current		
	RT 1	120 °C	RT 2	RT 1	120 °C	RT 2
0 ° control sample	118 ± 3	112 ± 2	116 ± 3	113 ± 11	110 ± 8	114 ± 7
Polystyrene interleaved	65 ± 3	1 ± 0.2	65 ± 4	68 ± 3	1 ± 0.2	66 ± 3

Table 3. Flexural properties of the interleaved and pure carbon fibre reinforced epoxy composites at room temperature (RT) and 120 °C.

Composite	Tensile properties				Compressive properties			
	Modulus/ GPa		Strength/ MPa		Modulus/ GPa		Strength/ MPa	
	RT	120 °C	RT	120 °C	RT	120 °C	RT	120 °C
0 ° control sample	145 ± 6	146 ± 13	1682 ± 67	1629 ± 94	127 ± 3	136 ± 5	1264 ± 132	657 ± 60
Polystyrene interleaved	88 ± 12	55 ± 6	867 ± 114	395 ± 62	66 ± 1	-	786 ± 64	-

Table 4. Tensile and compressive properties of the interleaved and pure carbon fibre reinforced epoxy composites at room temperature (RT) and 120 °C.

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